

Diagnostic and Therapeutic Challenges of Co-Infections in Endemic Regions: A Case Report of Concurrent Enteric Fever and Leptospirosis

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ABSTRACT

Infectious diseases are highly prevalent in developing countries, causing significant economic burden and contributing to high morbidity and mortality rates. Factors such as tropical climates, poor water and sanitation infrastructure, seasonal flooding, and limited healthcare resources exacerbate the vulnerability of these regions to endemic diseases. In Southeast Asia, including Pakistan, common infectious diseases like malaria, dengue fever, enteric fever, leptospirosis, urinary tract infections, community-acquired pneumonia, and tuberculosis pose substantial health challenges. Co-infections further complicate diagnosis and management, as exemplified in this case report of a 23-year-old male from Afghanistan residing in Pakistan. The patient presented with fever, jaundice, and pancytopenia, initially treated unsuccessfully with antimalarials and ciprofloxacin. Subsequent investigations revealed a co-infection of enteric fever and leptospirosis, highlighting the diagnostic complexities and resistance patterns complicating treatment. The patient eventually showed improvement upon receiving appropriate antibiotics based on culture sensitivities. This case underscores the intricate challenges faced by healthcare providers in managing co-infections and emphasizes the importance of accurate diagnosis and tailored antibiotic therapy in regions burdened by multiple endemic infectious diseases.

INTRODUCTION

Infectious diseases are pervasive in developing countries, imposing a significant economic burden and contributing substantially to morbidity and mortality.^[1,2] Several factors, such as the tropical or subtropical location, compromised water and sanitation systems, seasonal flooding, and limited resources for healthcare, make

these regions especially vulnerable to endemic diseases.^[1-4] Among the prevailing infectious diseases in Southeast Asia, including Pakistan, malaria, Dengue fever, enteric fever, leptospirosis, urinary tract infections, community-acquired pneumonia, and tuberculosis are of paramount concerns.^[1,2,5] Healthcare professionals in these areas encounter multifaceted challenges in the realms of diagnosis, management, and patient outcomes.^[1-5]

The complexity further deepens when co-infections occur, as they introduce new layers of intricacy in both diagnosis and management.^[4,6] Selecting appropriate antibiotics becomes an even more formidable task, especially when dealing with conditions such as enteric fever, which has been increasingly resistant to conventional treatments since 2016.^[7] In some instances, extreme drug resistance (XDR) variants have emerged.^[7,8] *Leptospira*, a spirochete commonly found in contaminated water sources, has the potential to co-infect individuals already suffering from enteric fever.^[4,7,9]

Unlike enteric fever, diagnosing leptospirosis heavily relies on serological tests, as conventional blood cultures and sensitivity assessments offer limited utility.^[4,9] Furthermore, the clinical presentations of both diseases can manifest in a multitude of ways, and the overlap or simultaneous occurrence of these clinical pictures often complicates the accuracy of clinical assessments.^[4,7,9]

This case report sheds light on the intricate web of challenges posed by co-infections in regions where typhoid, leptospirosis, dengue, malaria, tuberculosis, and other infectious diseases are prevalent.^[1,7] By highlighting the diagnostic and management difficulties faced in the wake of such co-infections, we aim to provide valuable insights into the complexities and potential solutions faced by healthcare providers in these areas."

CASE PRESENTATION

A 23-year-old male daily laborer from Afghanistan, residing in Pakistan, was referred to our facility from a private clinic. He presented with a complex clinical picture of fever, jaundice, and pancytopenia. On further exploration of his medical history, it was revealed that he had been experiencing high-grade fever associated with rigors and chills for the past three weeks, accompanied by bodyaches, myalgias, and a persistent headache. Additionally, he reported abdominal pain for two weeks and had developed dyspnea, profound fatigue, marked paleness, and concurrent pale-yellow sclera over the past week.

The patient had previously received oral antimalarials and ciprofloxacin, although these treatments did not provide relief. A peripheral blood smear indicated a high reticulocyte count of 15% and pancytopenia, including neutropenia, as revealed by the differential leukocyte count. Upon physical examination, the patient was febrile with a temperature of 105°F, exhibited a rapid pulse rate of 122, and displayed tachypnea. His overall condition appeared toxically unwell, and right upper quadrant tenderness, hepatosplenomegaly, yellow sclera, and anemic features were detected.

Laboratory investigations further uncovered pancytopenia. Elevated levels of LDH (607 U/L; normal range: 140-280 U/L), CRP (7 mg/L; normal range: <5 mg/L), and ferritin (453 ng/mL; normal range: 20-250 ng/mL) were noted. While PT/INR/APTT values were within the normal range, liver function tests indicated significantly elevated levels: total bilirubin was 10 mg/dL (normal range: 0.1-1.2 mg/dL) with direct bilirubin at 8.7 mg/dL (normal range: 0.0-0.3 mg/dL) and indirect bilirubin at 1.3 mg/dL. Additionally, ALT was 294 U/L (normal range: 7-56 U/L), ALP was 302 U/L (normal range: 44-147 U/L), and SGPT was 200 U/L (normal range: 7-56 U/L). Serology for hepatitis B, C, HIV, and dengue returned negative, and malarial parasites were not observed in the

patient's blood smear. Blood cultures, Leptospira serology, Brucella serology, and viral serology for hepatitis A and E, along with urine routine examination (R/E) and culture, were promptly submitted as per ward protocol.

The patient was initiated on ceftriaxone and piperacillin/tazobactam to address potential neutropenic sepsis, in addition to intravenous antimalarials. Despite several days of treatment, the patient displayed minimal improvement, prompting a shift to ceftriaxone, doxycycline, and intravenous azithromycin, while further investigations were initiated. During this period, hemoglobin levels continued to decline, liver function tests remained deranged, and the liver and spleen sizes showed little variation.

Later, blood culture results revealed Salmonella typhi sensitivity to azithromycin, co-trimoxazole, and meropenem, while resistance to ceftriaxone, piperacillin/tazobactam, cephalixin/sulbactam, and cefixime was identified. Upon initiation of the appropriate antibiotics, the patient exhibited a favorable response. Subsequent reports indicated declining LFTs (bilirubin= 6 mg, ALT= 216, ALP= 224), ultrasound findings demonstrated reduced liver span (from 20 cm to 16 cm) and a palpable spleen span (from 16 cm to 14 cm), and the patient regained the ability to take medications orally and walk independently.

Following these improvements, the patient was discharged and scheduled for a follow-up appointment in two weeks. In retrospect, the unique challenge in this case lay in deciphering a clinical presentation marked by hepatitis and obstructive jaundice, in which enteric fever had not been initially considered. The interplay between the two infections remained enigmatic, leaving us to question which one was the primary cause of the hepatitis and deranged liver function tests. However, once the administration of sensitive antibiotics was initiated, the patient's condition showed remarkable improvement.

Table 1: Shows Trend of Bichemical Tests Before and After Culture Sensitive Antibiotics Were Started

PARAMETER	BEFORE THE START OF APPROPRIATE (CULTURE SENSITIVE) ANTIBIOTICS			AFTER THE START OF APPROPRIATE (CULTURE SENSITIVE) ANTIBIOTICS				Normal Ranges
	23-11-2023	25-11-2023	28-11-2023	29-11-2023	02-12-2023	04-12-2023	07-12-2023	
WBC	2.2 * 10 ⁹	2.4 * 10 ⁹	1.9 * 10 ⁹	2.4 * 10 ⁹	3.5 * 10 ⁹	4.8 * 10 ⁹	7.6 * 10 ⁹	4.5 to 11.0 × 10 ⁹ /L
Hb	8.9 gm/dl	8.6 gm/dl	7.9 gm/dl	8.5 gm/dl	9.1 gm/dl	9.4 gm/dl	10.1 gm/dl	Male: 12.5 to 17.5 mg/dl Female: 11.5 to 16.5 mg/dl
Platelets	87000	76000	50500	64000	90000	115000	135000	150 to 400 × 10 ⁹ /L
CRP	7	12	34	34	12	5	2	<5 mg/L
ESR	23	35	44	35	21	15	6	<15 mm/hr
Serum Ferritin	453	546	765	654	523	356	190	20 to 250 ng/ml
LDH	607	708	785	725	654	450	270	140 to 280 U/L
ALT	294	356	453	412	280	138	45	7 to 56 U/L
AST	200	299	316	267	165	98	65	7 to 56 U/L
ALP	302	345	322	234	156	76	35	44 to 147 U/L
Total Bilirubin	10	12	12.6	11.6	9.1	5.6	1.3	0.1 to 1.2 mg/dl
Creatinine	1.5	1.2	1.7	1.3	1.1	0.9	0.6	0.7 to 1.3 mg/dl
Urea	34	33	29	22	23	14	11	10 to 20 mg/dl

Sodium	145	134	143	134	141	139	134	135 to 145 mEq/L
Potassium	4.1	4.2	5.1	4.7	3.7	3.6	5.1	3.6 to 5.2 millimoles per liter (mmol/L).
Chloride	98.3	99.2	101	104	98.3	107	104	96 to 106 MEq/l
WBC: White Blood Cells, Hb: Hemoglobin, CRP: C-Reactive Protein, ESR: Erythrocyte sedimentation rate, LDH: Lactate dehydrogenase, ALT: Alanine aminotransferase, AST: Aspartate aminotransferase,								
ALP: Alkaline phosphatase,								

DISCUSSION

Enteric fever, caused by the Gram-negative bacterium *Salmonella typhi*, is endemic in Pakistan, presenting a wide spectrum of clinical manifestations affecting 21 millions annually worldwide as per a report of WHO and about 161000 deaths excluding morbidities.^[1,11] Symptoms such as fever, body aches, hepatitis, and potential complications, including intestinal perforation, hepatic failure, abscesses, and multiple organ failure, challenge both diagnosis and management.^[11-14] In many developing countries, antibiotic misuse further complicates typhoid fever diagnosis due to getting negative culture report and the wide clinical presentation and complications.^[12,13]

Leptospira, a waterborne spirochete, is another infection often found alongside endemic diseases such as malaria, dengue, and enteric fever in tropical regions. It can be easily transmitted through the skin or mucous membranes. To diagnose *Leptospira*, the gold standard is the microscopic agglutination test, supported by ELISA serology. Gathering a detailed history regarding exposure to contaminated drinking water is of utmost importance. Knowledge of resistance patterns is essential for providing prompt empirical treatment.

Co-infection of *Leptospira* and typhoid fever is rare but reported in various cases, always posing a diagnostic dilemma to healthcare providers.^[4,7,10,14,15,16] These dual infections result in extended hospital stays, life-threatening complications, and increased financial burdens.^[4,7,10-13] In our unique case, the patient initially presented as acute hepatitis with pancytopenia. Empirical treatment was initiated to cover *Leptospira* and enteric fever. However, due to the diverse resistance patterns of enteric fever, our patient's hospital stay became particularly challenging, a presentation not previously reported to our knowledge."

CONCLUSION

This case report highlights the complexities and diagnostic challenges associated with co-infections in regions with high prevalence of infectious diseases. The case of a 23-year-old male presenting with fever, jaundice, and pancytopenia underscores the difficulties in identifying and managing overlapping clinical presentations of enteric fever and leptospirosis. The patient's initial treatment with empirical antibiotics was hindered by the presence of multidrug-resistant *Salmonella typhi*, illustrating the necessity for timely and accurate diagnostic methods, including blood cultures and sensitivity testing. Successful management was achieved through tailored antibiotic therapy based on culture results. This case emphasizes the critical need for healthcare providers in endemic regions to be vigilant for co-infections and to employ comprehensive diagnostic and therapeutic strategies to improve

patient outcomes. The report further advocates for enhanced surveillance and antibiotic stewardship to address the growing challenge of drug resistance in infectious diseases.

ABBREVIATIONS

ALT - Alanine Transaminase

AST - Aspartate Transaminase

ALP - Alkaline Phosphatase

CRP - C-Reactive Protein

ESR - Erythrocyte Sedimentation Rate

Hb - Hemoglobin

IV - Intravenous

LDH - Lactate Dehydrogenase

PT/INR/APTT - Prothrombin Time/International Normalized Ratio/Activated Partial Thromboplastin Time

R/E - Routine Examination

SGPT - Serum Glutamic Pyruvic Transaminase

WBC - White Blood Cells

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